

MULTISCALE MODELING OF CARBON FIBER/CARBON NANOTUBE/EPOXY HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the multiscale modeling of hybrid composites composed of carbon fibers (CFs), carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and three different epoxy systems (di-, tri-, and tetra-functional epoxies). The mechanical properties of the hybrid composites are predicted for CNT/epoxy composites with randomly oriented CNTs and for CF/CNT/epoxy systems with aligned CFs and randomly oriented CNTs. The results indicate that in the CNT/epoxy systems the epoxy type has a significant influence on the elastic properties. For the CF/CNT/epoxy hybrid composites, the axial modulus is highly influenced by CF concentration, while the transverse modulus is primarily affected by the CNT volume fraction.

1 INTRODUCTION

The diffusion of carbon fiber (CF) composites attests to the demand of stiff-yet-lightweight materials. By employing materials with high specific stiffness and specific strength, light-weighting offers such advantages as increased fuel efficiency and lower emissions. Additionally, CF composites can be tailored to handle expected loads. However, these composites presently demonstrate some weaknesses that limit their applicability: low compressive strength, susceptibility to delaminate upon impact, and low thermal conductivity. It is conjectured that the inclusion of nanoparticles in the matrix may address these issues collectively. This multiscale approach may provide a breakthrough to achieving the next generation of CF composites.

The noteworthy mechanical and thermal properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) make these nanoparticles attractive candidates for enhancing the mechanical and thermal deficiencies of traditional CF composites. For the success of CNT-enhanced composites, the well-known difficulties of obtaining good CNT dispersion and good CNT-matrix interaction have been addressed extensively. Among the numerous studies conducted, some have sought to understand what matrix characteristics promote good CNT-matrix interaction. Korayem et al. compared two different commercial epoxies used in reinforcing civil structures and found that the more ductile epoxy saw the greater improvement in Young's Modulus for two forms of CNTs, namely CNT powder and CNT masterbatch [1]. To corroborate the nanocomposite stiffness results, the strength of the CNT-matrix interaction was qualitatively assessed using SEM to examine CNTs at the fracture surface, whether the CNTs tended to be extracted from the matrix or fractured. Similarly, Ci and Bai investigated the effect of the epoxy matrix stiffness by controlling the cure time and the ratio of hardener to resin [2]. It was shown that soft, ductile epoxies demonstrate the greatest improvement in Young's Modulus for 0.5 wt% of CNT; whereas, no improvement in modulus was observed for the stiffest epoxy used. Additional studies have confirmed that stiff epoxies are not well enhanced by CNTs [3-5]. However, this principle is not necessarily true when the CNT is functionalized in order to covalently bond to the matrix [6].

Molecular modeling provides additional insights by simulating the molecular interactions between a polymer and CNT. This computational approach has also been utilized to study what molecular features allow for good adhesion to CNTs. For example, it has been concluded that the presence of benzene [7] and sulfur [8] in the polymer promotes good interaction with CNT. Typically, studies that compare different polymers interacting with CNT are performed with an oligomer and CNT in a vacuum [8-12]. Yang et al. used Molecular Dynamics (MD) interaction energy calculations for CNTs with four different polymers containing benzene rings [9]. Attention was given to the orientation of the benzene rings to the CNT, and it was shown that the polymers that could align its benzene rings

parallel to the CNT demonstrated significantly better interaction. It was concluded by the authors that this was due to better pi-pi stacking. Additionally, the non-bonded adhesion of different epoxy monomers and curing agents to CNTs has been compared using MD [7, 13]. Wu et al. built uncured models of EPON 862/DETDA and EPON 862/DETA, both with CNT, and determined that the DETDA curing agent demonstrates better interaction with CNT than DETA [7]. While modeling the individual epoxy resin and hardener monomers with CNT can shed light on the initial pre-crosslinked state, the network structure produced upon curing may determine the final adhesion properties. This has been demonstrated by Li et al. in studying the interaction between an epoxy and silica substrate in which the interaction was shown to increase with increasing crosslink density [14].

The objective of this study is to build MD models of three different crosslinked epoxy systems with CNT and analyze the mechanical properties. To predict the effective properties of a realistic CNT/epoxy nanocomposite, a micromechanics approach will be utilized. Similarly, the properties of a hybrid CF/CNT/epoxy composite will also be predicted for each epoxy type.

2 MD MODELING

Three unique epoxy systems were modeled with CNT. Figure 1 provides the monomers of each epoxy and the skeletal structures of each monomer. For all systems, the same hardener, diethyltoluenediamine (DETDA), was used. However, various resin monomers were chosen: bisphenol F diglycidyl ether (BFDGE, EPON 862), tri-glycidyl para-amino phenol (TGAP, Araldite MY 0510), and tetra-glycidyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (TGDDM, Araldite MY 721). Note that the number of reactive epoxide groups is unique for each resin molecule indicating that the functionality of each resin is distinct. The functionalities of BFDGE, TGAP, and TGDDM are 2, 3, and 4 respectively. Thus, we will use the names Di, Tri, and Tetra to refer to BFDGE/DETDA, TGAP/DETDA, and TGDDM/DETDA as indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Three epoxy systems modeled.

The ratio of resin monomers to hardener monomers was chosen so that exactly two epoxide groups were present for each amine group. Since each amine group can react with two epoxide groups this provides for a stoichiometric ratio of resin to hardener. For the Di, Tri, and Tetra systems, the ratio of resin to hardener molecules was 2:1, 4:3, and 1:1 respectively (Table 1).

Table 1: Details of epoxy models

EPOXY	f_r	NO. OF RESINS	NO. OF HARDENERS	RESIN TO HARDENER RATIO	TOTAL NO. OF ATOMS
Di	2	90	45	2:1	5,265
Tri	3	84	63	4:3	5,229
Tetra	4	57	57	1:1	5,244

2.1 Model construction

A periodic simulation box was created containing the epoxy monomer models. The OPLS all-atom force field was implemented in LAMMPS [15] for building the monomer models and assembling and cross-linking the nanocomposite system [16]. The initial mass density was 0.09-0.10 g/cm³. A 100 ps fixed-volume simulation was performed in which the monomers were allowed to mix. Simultaneously, the temperature was ramped down from 600 to 300 K. The 5 independent samples of each epoxy type were distinguished by setting different random initial velocities. Thus, for each sample, the monomers mixed in a unique manner. Thereafter the simulation box was gradually reduced in size to a density of about 1.05 g/cm³ over 4 ns with molecular minimizations performed every 200 ps. The new box dimensions were determined such that the length in z-direction was 41.6 Å to accommodate the CNT. During densification, the temperature and timestep were set to 300 K and 1 fs respectively.

A cylindrical void was created by applying the “fix indent” command in LAMMPS during a 100 ps simulation. The radius of the cylindrical region in which atoms would be repelled was increased from 0 to 7.4 Å over the course of the simulation. The volume remained fixed and the temperature was set to 300 K.

For all models, an unfunctionalized, zigzag (10,0) CNT was inserted into the void. The resulting nanocomposite models all contained about 12 wt% CNT as shown in Table 2. The CNT and epoxy monomers were equilibrated for 6 ns at 300 K using the NVT ensemble.

TABLE 2. NANOCOMPOSITE MODELS

EPOXY	CNT WT%	CROSSLINK DENSITY	DENSITY g/cm ³
Di	11.7	0.74 ± 0.04	1.257 ± 0.006
Tri	12.2	0.79 ± 0.02	1.261 ± 0.006
Tetra	12.3	0.74 ± 0.02	1.232 ± 0.008

The epoxy monomers were crosslinked for 1 ns at 300 K while the CNT atoms remained fixed. No covalent bonds were formed between the CNT and epoxy. Further details on the crosslinking procedure is described in a previous work [17]. For each epoxy type, the average crosslink density of 5 samples is given in Table 2. Both the Di and Tetra systems averaged 74% crosslink density. However, the Tri epoxy is able to obtain a higher average crosslink density of 79%. Previous pure epoxy models also showed higher crosslink densities for the Tri system [17].

Figure 2: Representative CNT (yellow) and epoxy (CPK coloring) model.

Once, the crosslinked structure of epoxy was established, the nanocomposite system was imported into ReaxFF [18]. The Liu et al. parameter set with low gradient corrections was selected [19]. The hydroxyl groups that were created upon crosslinking were not assigned angle or dihedral parameters in OPLS [17]. As a result, the conformation of some hydroxyl groups were unstable in ReaxFF. This was rectified by allowing the hydroxyl group hydrogens to reposition with limited kinetic energy while all other atoms remained fixed. This was accomplished during a 100 ps simulation using the “temp/rescale” and “fix viscous” LAMMPS commands. The timestep was set to 0.1 fs for all simulations using ReaxFF. Afterwards, all atoms were gradually brought into motion by ramping the temperature from 1 to 300 K over 100 ps.

The ReaxFF CNT/epoxy models were equilibrated over 2.1 ns at 300 K. Using the NPT ensemble, the Nose-Hoover barostat was set to maintain 1 atm of pressure on all sides of the simulation box. Table 2 gives the average mass density after equilibration for each epoxy type. The final simulation box dimensions were roughly 35x35x42 Å where the z-direction is the axial direction of the CNT. A completed CNT/epoxy MD model is shown in Figure 2.

2.2 Mechanical deformation

Each crosslinked, equilibrated model was subjected to uniaxial tension and shear deformation simulations. Three tension simulations were conducted per model: tension in the x-, y-, and z-directions. The simulation box was gradually deformed up to 10% engineering strain over 500 ps resulting in a strain rate of $2 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The NPT ensemble was implemented to allow for Poisson's contractions. A Nose-Hoover barostat was set to maintain 1 atm of pressure on the contracting sides. Additionally, three simple shear simulations were performed for each model: shear in the xy-, xz-, and yz- planes. The NVT ensemble was selected, and the models were deformed up to 5% shear strain over 250 ps ($2 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$ strain rate). All deformation simulations were carried out at 300 K with a timestep of 0.1 fs.

From each deformation simulation, the stress-strain data was fit with a linear regression model for strains up to about 3% strain. Figure 3 provides an example stress-strain plot obtained from uniaxial tension transverse to the CNT. The Poisson's ratios were also obtained from each tension simulation. The lateral strains were plotted with respect to the tensile strain and fit with a linear regression model for tensile strains up to 3.5%.

Figure 3: Representative stress-strain curve with linear fit

TABLE 3. ELASTIC MODULI FROM MD SIMULATION

EPOXY	E_A GPa	E_T GPa	ν_A	ν_T	G_A GPa	G_T GPa
Di	71.2 ± 1.8	3.88 ± 0.78	0.39 ± 0.18	0.61 ± 0.08	1.19 ± 0.25	1.63 ± 0.18
Tri	76.0 ± 0.5	5.40 ± 0.84	0.33 ± 0.09	0.54 ± 0.06	1.60 ± 0.46	2.19 ± 0.32
Tetra	72.9 ± 0.8	5.09 ± 0.77	0.35 ± 0.12	0.56 ± 0.09	1.50 ± 0.46	1.79 ± 0.32

The mechanical properties obtained from MD simulation are given in Table 3. The properties listed are the axial and transverse Young's moduli (E_A and E_T), axial and transverse Poisson's ratio (ν_A and ν_T), and axial and transverse shear moduli (G_A and G_T). For all Young's moduli and shear moduli, the Di model provides the least average value and Tri model provides the greatest average value. Even though there is considerable variation in values for some moduli, the consistency in the order Tri>Tetra>Di supports making such a distinction. There are statistically significant differentiations that can be asserted in support of this ordering. Most apparently, the Tri model resulted in an axial Young's modulus of 76.0 GPa, clearly outperforming the Di (71.2 GPa) and Tetra (72.9 GPa) models.

For the transverse Young's modulus results, the Di model yields a value of 3.88 GPa which is undoubtedly the least stiff of the three epoxies. The E_T values for the Tri and Tetra are 5.40 and 5.09 GPa, respectively, but due to the standard deviations, this difference is not statistically significant. Either additional models or larger models would be required to fully assert that the Tri epoxy provides the greatest values for all stiffness properties.

3 MICROMECHANICS

3.1 Randomly dispersed CNT in epoxy

First, the properties of an aligned CNT/epoxy system were obtained for various epoxy types, CNT wt%, and CNT aspect ratios. This was accomplished using MAC/GMC [20]. The properties of the MD CNT/epoxy model (Table 3) was input into subcell MD , and the remaining subcells were assigned the bulk epoxy properties shown in Table 4. A 2D representative unit cell (RUC) was employed for infinitely long CNT, and a 3D RUC was used for finite CNT aspect ratios. To consider different amounts of CNT, the ratio of subcell MD to the entire RUC was adjusted. The overall wt% of CNT $w_{CNT/RUC}$ can be determined by

$$w_{CNT/RUC} = w_{CNT/MD} \times w_{MD/RUC} \quad (1)$$

where $w_{CNT/MD}$ is the CNT wt% of the MD model (Table 2) and $w_{MD/RUC}$ is the wt% of the MD model to the entire RUC. Moreover, $w_{MD/RUC}$ can be found from the density of the MD model ρ_{MD} , the bulk epoxy density ρ_B , and the volume fractions of the subcell MD and bulk subcells to the RUC, $v_{MD/RUC}$ and $v_{B/RUC}$, respectively:

$$w_{MD/RUC} = \frac{\rho_{MD} v_{MD/RUC}}{\rho_{MD} v_{MD/RUC} + \rho_B v_{B/RUC}} \quad (2)$$

The densities of the MD models and bulk epoxy are given in Table 2 and Table 4. The bulk epoxy properties were obtained from previous MD modeling efforts [17]. Thus, from Equations (1) and (2), the overall CNT wt% could be calculated given the RUC geometry.

The properties of aligned CNT/epoxy were integrated over all directions to predict the effective properties of randomly dispersed CNT in epoxy [21, 22]. While the aligned material is transversely isotropic, the final nanocomposite is isotropic. The properties for CNT/epoxy obtained in this step were re-input into MAC/GMC to examine the hybrid lamina as described in the following section. Note that this method treats the CNT as being perfectly dispersed.

TABLE 4. PROPERTIES USED FOR BULK EPOXY

EPOXY	E GPa	ν	DENSITY g/cm ³
Di	3.51	0.37	1.222
Tri	4.94	0.37	1.235
Tetra	5.30	0.35	1.221

3.2 CF/CNT/Epoxy lamina

The effective properties of a CF/CNT/epoxy hybrid composite were calculated via MAC/GMC. Here we considered unidirectional CF (as in a composite lamina) in a CNT-enhanced matrix. The properties of random CNT/epoxy as determined in the previous micromechanics step was input as the matrix, and the AS4 carbon fiber properties shown in Table 5 were selected. The matrix and fiber properties were assigned to a 2D RUC consisting of 676 subcells to approximate a circular fiber. This RUC is available in MAC/GMC as designated by the architecture ID number 13. The fibers were arranged in a square packing array. In this manner, the properties of a CF/CNT/epoxy lamina were

obtained for various epoxy types, CNT wt% (with respect to the matrix), CNT aspect ratio, and CF volume fraction.

TABLE 5. AS4 CARBON FIBER PROPERTIES

E_A (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	ν_A	ν_T	G_A (GPa)
235	15	0.20	0.07	27

4 RESULTS

The effective Young's moduli of random, infinitely long CNT in epoxy is shown in Figure 4. Both the Tri and Tetra epoxies demonstrate excellent stiffness for all CNT concentrations and aspect ratios. The nanoparticle-matrix interaction and load transfer characteristics can be inferred from the *increase* in the modulus relative to the bulk matrix. For example, we see that the Tri system results in good load transfer and allows the CNT/Tri nanocomposite to surpass the CNT/Tetra system for high CNT wt%. (For 5 wt% of infinite CNTs, the predicted moduli for the Tri and Tetra models are 9.73 and 9.60 GPa, respectively. Similarly, for 5 wt% of CNTs with aspect ratio of 1000, the predicted moduli for the Tri and Tetra models are 9.60 and 9.48 GPa.) For 5 wt% infinite CNT, the Di and Tri epoxy moduli both were improved by about 4.8 GPa. However, the Tetra epoxy was improved by about 4.3 GPa. Since the bulk Tetra epoxy is the stiffest out of the three studied, this matches with experiment observations that stiffer matrices are not as well-improved by unfunctionalized CNT as softer epoxies [1-5].

Figure 4: Effective Young's Modulus of random CNT/epoxy for various epoxy types and CNT aspect ratios

While the effect of the nanoparticle-matrix interaction can be observed in Figure 4, it is not the most significant factor. Even though the Di epoxy demonstrates good nanoparticle-matrix load transfer, the CNT/Di nanocomposite remains the most compliant (just as the bulk Di epoxy) and cannot supersede CNT/Tetra at reasonable CNT concentrations. Additionally, the Tri epoxy only slightly supersedes the Tetra epoxy at high CNT wt%. Thus, no distinction in non-bonded CNT-epoxy interaction resulted in any dramatic improvement with respect to the other epoxies. While the CNT-epoxy interaction does indeed contribute, the bulk matrix stiffness appears to be the dominant factor when comparing the relative nanocomposite performance for different epoxies.

Notwithstanding the differences discussed above, all epoxy types are predicted to be greatly enhanced by well-dispersed CNT. While the Tetra epoxy is noted to possess the weakest nanoparticle-matrix interaction, 5 wt% infinite CNT results in a predicted increase in Young's modulus of 81%. Therefore, we do not expect the weaker CNT-Tetra interface to altogether inhibit reinforcement.

Figure 5 shows a design map of the CF/CNT/epoxy system for the di-functional resin epoxy. It is clear that increases in CF volume fraction have a strong influence on the axial modulus, while increases in CNT volume fraction primarily dictate the transverse modulus. This design map provides

a simple means to choose the desired axial and transverse properties and determine the corresponding reinforcement volume fractions to achieve the desired properties.

The influence of different epoxy types on the transverse modulus of a CF/CNT/epoxy lamina is shown in Figure 6. Similar to the CNT/epoxy nanocomposite results, the Tri and Tetra epoxies provide for the stiffest hybrid composites for all CNT concentrations. The results shown in Figure 6 were obtained for a CF volume fraction of 0.60. The CF/CNT/Tri and CF/CNT/Tetra models outperformed the CF/CNT/Di for other CF loadings as well. While the axial modulus is dominated by the CF and only minorly affected by CNT, we observed the axial modulus was slightly greater (about 1 GPa) for the Tri and Tetra epoxies when compared to the Di epoxy for various CNT concentrations.

Figure 5: Predicted axial and transverse moduli for CF/CNT/epoxy with the Di epoxy. Various fiber volume fractions and CNT wt% are shown. CNT is treated as having infinite aspect ratio.

Figure 6: Effective transverse modulus for CF/CNT/epoxy hybrid laminas for various epoxy types. Volume fraction of CF is 0.60, and CNT is treated as having infinite aspect ratio.

5 CONCLUSIONS

By simulating CNT embedded in multiple epoxy matrices, the mechanical response was compared to determine what types of epoxies may be desired for structural nanocomposites. The MD results demonstrate the tri-functional resin epoxy paired with CNT outperforms the other models. In order to determine whether or not the excellent properties of the CNT/Tri MD model ultimately translates into a superior nanocomposite, an atomistically-informed multiscale approach was employed to predict the behavior of realistic composites. The multiscale model indicates that the Tri epoxy does indeed deliver the highest modulus nanocomposite and CF/CNT/epoxy hybrid lamina for high CNT loadings. However, the Tri epoxy only slightly outperforms the Tetra epoxy at these concentrations. Thus, we

recommend both the Tri and Tetra epoxies. Due to the relatively compliant bulk properties, the Di epoxy does not appear to have the potential to yield a nanocomposite or hybrid composite as mechanically stiff as the other epoxies studied for reasonable CNT loadings. Recall that we assert all stated results for *unfunctionalized* CNT reinforcement. For further analysis, we will investigate the interfacial and interphase properties directly from the MD models to corroborate the CNT-epoxy load transfer capability inferred from the mechanical data.

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